

Quantum Non-Gaussian States of Superfluid Helium Vibrations

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Quantum non-Gaussian states of phononic systems coupled to light are essential for fundamental studies of single-phonon mechanics and direct applications in quantum technology. Although nonclassical mechanical states have already been demonstrated, the more challenging quantum non-Gaussianity of such states remains limited. Using photon counting detection, we propose the quantum non-Gaussian generation of few-phonon states of low-temperature vibrating superfluid Helium. We predict the quantum non-Gaussian depth of such phononic states and investigate their robustness under relevant mechanical heating. As the quality of such phononic states is very high, we confirm a single-phonon bunching capability to further classify such states for future mechanical experiments. Moreover, we predict increasing capability for force sensing and thermometry for increasing heralded phonon numbers.

1 Introduction

Quantum physics and technology have two paradigmatic directions, with discrete and continuous variables encoding quantum states [1–3]. Each direction has its own advantages and weaknesses, and occasionally there is an effort to combine both to understand further their fundamental interplay and, moreover, to get an advantage for quantum technology [4, 5]. Quantum cavity optomechanics [6, 7] has been seemingly leaning mostly towards the continuous-variable domain [1] as dictated by the experimental prevalence of linearized optomechanical dynamics and heterodyne detection of light as the main method of the mechanical displacement detection [8]. This can be traced from the first treatises of ultimate precision of gravity-wave detectors [9–11] to modern works [12–14]. Experimental studies were gradually focusing on approaching ground states of mechanical oscillators [15, 16], and eventually squeezed [17, 18] and entangled states [19, 20].

In recent years, a sizeable effort has been dedicated to developing the control of optomechanical systems at the level of single excitations. Notable experiments with discrete-variable evaluation of optomechanical two-mode squeezing have been performed [21–24]. There are particularly interesting results coming from adding and subtracting single phonons of mechanical oscillations via counting photons resulting from the upconversion of phonons of thermal mechanical vibrations. Following theoretical proposals [25, 26], elaborate experiments were able to verify novel out-of-equilibrium character of the resulting states via observing non-Gaussian quadrature distributions [27, 28] or increased intensity auto-correlation [29]. To more precisely characterize the single-phonon control of mechanical motion, further tests are required.

The photon counting detectors possess nonlinearity which is otherwise still challenging to achieve in optomechanical systems at the quantum level. The detector nonlinearity allows us to immediately enter the domain of quantum non-Gaussian (QNG) optomechanics [30]. Previous notable advances in non-Gaussian mechanical motion were in electromechanics where experiments included coupling mechanics to superconducting discrete-level devices [31–36]. Quantum non-Gaussianity is an important prerequisite for many tasks in quantum technology as demonstrated by the experiments in other fields [37–43], is actively pursued experimentally in quantum optomechanics [30, 43].

Here, inspired by the superfluid Helium setup reported in Refs. [29, 44], we propose, analyze, and confirm the possibility of the conditional QNG mechanical states, induced by photon-counting detectors. To achieve conclusive results and comparison with other experiments, we apply criteria [45, 46] of multiphonon

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and multiphoton quantum non-Gaussianity to these states, and estimate their bunching capability [47] and suitability for quantum sensing [37]. Our results show that the state-of-the-art optomechanical experiment is capable of creating, for the first time, high-quality QNG states of mechanical motion, which are applicable to quantum sensing. In near future, these can be used as a phononic resource in quantum error correction [48], for quantum sensing of extremely small forces [49, 50], or in fundamental tests [51–53] already proposed for photons. Our main focus is on the superfluid He systems, however, the analysis based on the ubiquitous linearized optomechanical interaction [54, 55], and the standard theory of photon counting apply to other opto-/electromechanical systems.

2 Results

Absolute thresholds for k -phonon quantum non-Gaussianity

k	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
$p_k^{\mathcal{G}}$	0.478	0.557	0.593	0.612	0.625	0.637	0.641	0.646	0.650	0.654

Figure 1: Scheme of conditional addition/subtraction of phonons with subsequent verification. (a) A sequence of detuned pulses drives the optomechanical cavity. Leaking resonant light is detected by a photon-counting detector (APD or a multiplexed version). (b) Circuit diagram of the process. (c) Frequency-domain illustration of the resonantly enhanced scattering processes (see Section 4.1). Detection of a photon heralds a scattering event which creates/removes a phonon, based on the drive detuning. (d,e) Quantum non-Gaussianity criteria. (d) Example of evaluation. In the plane of probabilities (p_0, p_1) [$p_i = \langle i | \rho | i \rangle$], Gaussian states can only occupy the area filled with cyan (\mathcal{G}) bounded by a loss-resilient threshold used for optical states. The green horizontal line shows the absolute threshold $p_1^{\mathcal{G}} = 0.478$ used to quantify mechanical states (see below). An initially visibly non-Gaussian state (ρ_1 , orange dot) gradually thermalizes (darker dots) until it reaches $\rho_2 \in \mathcal{G}$ and further. The admixed noise required to reach ρ_2 is the *quantum non-Gaussianity depth* of ρ_1 . (e) Absolute threshold probabilities $p_k^{\mathcal{G}}$ for multiphonon quantum non-Gaussianity (see Section 2.2) for $0 \leq k < 5$. The table below includes values of $p_k^{\mathcal{G}}$ for larger k .

2.1 Phonon control of superfluid Helium optomechanics

We consider an optomechanical system formed by mechanical fluctuations of the superfluid Helium in a fiber cavity as reported in [29, 44]. Such a system exhibits radiation-pressure-induced coupling between the optical field and mechanical density waves of the Helium. In the presence of coherent optical driving, this coupling can be well described by the standard linearized model of optomechanical interaction [6, 54] (Fig. 1 a). In particular, driven on the lower mechanical sideband (red detuning, see Fig. 1 c), the system performs an excitations swap between the intracavity light and the mechanical oscillator. Such interaction is described by the Hamiltonian $H_{BS} = g a_m a_c^\dagger + \text{h.c.}$, where a_m [a_c] is the annihilation operator of the mechanics [cavity field], g is the optomechanical coupling rate. In the case of driving on the upper sideband (blue detuning), an optomechanical two-mode squeezing interaction (Hamiltonian $H_{TMS} = g a_m a_c + \text{h.c.}$) is realized. Combining a weak interaction of one of these kinds with a single- or multi-photon detection in the leaking light, it is possible to conditionally approximately add (subtract) a single or multiple phonons

to (from) the superfluid Helium [29, 44] (Fig. 1 b). The enabling idea of these operations is illustrated in Fig. 1 (b). Given vacuum optical input, the detection of a photon in the optical output indicates that a scattering of a drive photon took place. This in turn heralds the addition (or subtraction) of a mechanical phonon. The corresponding (unnormalized) conditional quantum state ρ_{cond} of the mechanics is related to the initial state ρ_0 as

$$\rho_{\text{cond}}^{\text{Add}} = \mathbb{A}[\rho_0] \approx a_m^\dagger \rho_0 a_m, \quad \rho_{\text{cond}}^{\text{Sub}} = \mathbb{S}[\rho_0] \approx a_m \rho_0 a_m^\dagger. \quad (1)$$

Due to the technical imperfections in the system (non-unit detection, optical losses, mechanical decoherence, dark counts of the heralding detector, etc.), these states are not exactly single-phonon-subtracted or -added. A similar technique has been successfully used in experiments with optical photons [56, 57], and atoms [42, 58]. For a more formal theoretical discussion, see supplementary materials (SM). Using sequences of operations \mathbb{A} and \mathbb{S} , or using photon-number-resolving detectors, it is possible to perform multiple approximate additions and subtractions thereof. In particular, heralding the mechanical state upon coincidence detections of the output light in a Hanbury-Brown and Twiss (HBT) type of scheme [59] performs an approximate addition or subtraction of two phonons at a time. A similar result can be obtained by repeatedly adding/subtracting a single phonon twice (see comparison in Section 2.2).

Here, we consider in detail the protocol to conditionally create single- and multi-phonon-added mechanical states, and verify their quantum-mechanical properties towards QNG statistics. At the heart of this study is the canonical pump-and-probe protocol (Fig. 1 (a-c)) that involves a sequence of optical blue-detuned write and red-detuned verification pulses sent to the optomechanical cavity. All the pulses but the last one are used to perform the heralded creation of the conditional mechanical state upon registration of scattered photons by an on-off detector (APD). The last pulse is red-detuned and is used to swap the conditional quantum state of the mechanical oscillator to the state of the leaking light for verification. We consider possible delays between the pulses during which the mechanical oscillator only thermalizes towards equilibrium with the mechanical environment (characterized by damping rate γ and mean thermal occupation n_{th}). We assume the verification is also performed via multiplexed photon counting (instead of only a single APD), estimate possible visible non-classical effects, and find optimal regimes of operation of the optomechanical protocol.

2.2 Phonon-added thermal states

Phonon subtraction and addition are inherently conditional nonlinear operations capable of driving the mechanical oscillator to non-Gaussian single- or multi-phonon states. The non-Gaussianity of phonon-number states manifests itself in the shape and negativities of the Wigner function, however, a more detailed evaluation and more precise classification, including depth of quantum non-Gaussianity (see Fig. 1 d), is possible by evaluation of multiphonon contributions of the non-Gaussian states. Moreover, such evaluation can use direct detection of QNG features using high-quality single photon counters, as has been performed in quantum optics [60], without the need for a complex tomography reconstruction. Drawing inspiration from Refs. [45, 46], we compare the phonon-number contributions $\langle k | \rho_{\text{cond}} | k \rangle$ of conditional mechanical state ρ_{cond} with the thresholds peculiar to multiphoton QNG states. The thresholds (illustrated in Fig. 1 e, also see the table in Fig. 1) show for each non-negative integer k , the maximal probability attainable by states that are the result of Gaussian operations applied to states from the space spanned by all lower Fock states $|i\rangle$, $0 \leq i < k$. Formally, the threshold probabilities for each k are defined as

$$p_k^{\mathcal{G}} = \max_{\alpha, r, \{c_i\}} |\langle k | \hat{D}(\alpha) \hat{S}(r) \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} c_i |i\rangle \rangle|^2. \quad (2)$$

where $\hat{D}(\alpha) = \exp[\alpha^* a - \alpha a^\dagger]$ is a Gaussian displacement operator, and $\hat{S}(r) = \exp[r(a^\dagger)^2 - r^* a^2]$ is a Gaussian squeezing operator. The coefficients c_i are arbitrary, but must obey $\sum_i |c_i|^2 = 1$. The hierarchy of thresholds (2) gradually selects only such approximate mechanical Fock states where adding QNG features by the detection with more clicks is guaranteed.

In Fig. 2 we analyze the non-Gaussianity of the two-phonon-added mechanical states. Starting with the initial thermal state of the mechanical oscillator characterized by occupation n_0 , we compare the addition by two subsequent heralding events and by a single heralding via an HBT-like scheme. We consider a realistic optomechanical interaction described by the superfluid Helium parameters reported in Refs. [29, 44] including thermal decoherence via coupling to the environment with mean occupation $n_{\text{th}} = 1.2$. The mechanical states are evaluated at the instant right after the latest heralding event.

First, we observe that ideally starting from the ground state of the mechanical oscillator, both heralding methods reach a nearly-perfect Fock state ($|1\rangle$ or $|2\rangle$) with the imperfections due to the presence of the

mechanical thermal environment. For two additions, heralding by the HBT detection yields a slightly better result compared to two subsequent single-photon additions. This advantage is due to the shorter overall time of the interaction and consequently a slightly lower influence of the thermal noise. As a result, the purity and the two-phonon contribution of the HBT-heralded state is higher. Correspondingly the heralded states from both methods exhibit strong two-phonon non-Gaussianity according to the criteria from [46].

We estimate the non-Gaussianity depth of the heralded mechanical state by finding the mean number of thermal phonons to be added to this state to make it lose the two-phonon non-Gaussianity. To this end, we note that being coupled at the rate γ to the thermal bath for the time interval of duration τ , the mechanical oscillator undergoes a transformation that in the Heisenberg picture can be written as

$$a_m(t + \tau) = e^{-\gamma\tau/2} a_m(t) + \sqrt{1 - e^{-\gamma\tau}} a_{\text{th}}. \quad (3)$$

Here γ is the viscous damping rate of the mechanical oscillator, and a_{th} denotes the effective annihilation operator of a thermal oscillator representing the mechanical environment (see SM for theory details). The mean occupation of the state described by $a_m(t + \tau)$, therefore, has two contributions: one from the decaying initial state (described by $a_m(t)$), and another one from the phonons entering from the bath. The mechanical state eventually loses its QNG properties, and a convenient method of quantifying this process of de-Gaussification is by computing the mean number of thermal phonons that have entered the system from the bath. This can be done by evaluating the mean occupation of the second contribution in Eq. (3):

$$n_{\text{depth}} = \sqrt{1 - e^{-\gamma\tau}} \langle a_{\text{th}}^\dagger a_{\text{th}} \rangle \approx \gamma\tau n_{\text{th}}. \quad (4)$$

To find the depth of quantum non-Gaussianity or Wigner negativity, we determine the duration τ required for the heralded state to lose the corresponding property due to thermalization. We assume γ and n_{th} take the experimental values reported in Refs. [29, 44], and compute the resulting n_{depth} .

Thermal occupation of the initial mechanical state reduces the quality and the QNG depth of the heralded states. This is illustrated by the yellow lines (bars) in Fig. 2. Initial mechanical occupation $n_0 \approx 0.2$ is the highest that still allows the two-phonon added mechanical state to exhibit the two-phonon QNG (if heralding is by a coincidence HBT-like detection, the threshold occupation for two subsequent APD heralding is slightly lower). Notably, the states heralded using either method have visibly non-Gaussian Wigner functions, whose negativity vanishes at much higher initial occupations ($n_0 > 10$). This illustrates the importance of precise characterization of QNG features of the quantum states under study.

As the predicted quality of the heralded phonon-number state is high, we investigate the bunching capability of the created non-Gaussian states. The capability to bunch is highly relevant for the future linearized optomechanical arrays forming counterparts to trapped ion experiments, applicable in quantum sensing [61] and boson sampling experiments [62]. To make such a test for future optomechanical experiments, following the approach of Ref. [47, 63] for photons, we consider multiple copies of the conditional mechanical state entering a linear multiport mixing device. At the output of the mixer, we assume an extreme testing event, all phonons conditionally bunching to a single channel. We then compute an unnormalized Wigner function of the quantum state in this channel, to evaluate the capability of the output state to exhibit negativities. The expression for the Wigner function of the output state is in SM.

The simulated Wigner functions are in Fig. 3. Multiple copies of heralded mechanical states show the capability to bunch forming higher-order Fock states at the output of a linear quantum network. Importantly, the bunching capabilities of conditional mechanical states are mostly determined by the thermal noise added during the conditional operation. In particular, the visibly different conditional states in Fig. 2, show exactly the same bunching results (the identical panel for bunching of $N = 5$ copies of the two-phonon-added state is not shown). This is because we assumed equal durations of the heralding pulse, and consequently the amount of thermal noise added during the heralding pulse is equal. Instead, in Fig. 3 b we show bunching of $N = 5$ copies of two-phonon-added state after additional decoherence, sufficient to lose the 10-phonon quantum non-Gaussianity.

2.3 Verification of quantum non-Gaussianity

Subsequently, we investigate the possibility of verifying the QNG features of the mechanical heralded state by swapping its state to a leaking pulse of light. The swapping is performed via a red-detuned pulse of classical laser driving which enables a beam-splitter-like interaction $H_{\text{BS}} = g a_m a_c^\dagger + \text{h.c.}$ in the optomechanical cavity. The phonons upconverted to photons leak into the detection channel, and can be registered by an optical detector. From the linear optomechanics theory, we can derive the connection between the quantum state of the mechanics at the initial instant of the readout pulse $t = 0$, and the

Figure 2: Quantum non-Gaussianity of (a) single- and (b) two-phonon-added thermal mechanical state performed via blue-detuned pulses with heralding upon leaking photon detection. Single-phonon addition is performed via a single heralding (A). Two-phonon addition in (b) is either via a single pulse with HBT-like coincidence detection for heralding (darker lines) or, alternatively, two subsequent pulses with heralding upon a single APD detection from each pulse (lighter-colored lines). Blue lines (bars) correspond to the initial ground state of mechanics ($n_0 = 0$), yellow lines to $n_0 \approx 0.2$, the initial occupation at which the 2-phonon non-Gaussianity of $\mathbb{A}_2(\rho_0)$ vanishes. Plots in the main panels show the cuts of the Wigner functions of the heralded mechanical states (the Wigner functions are rotationally symmetric). Numbers near dips of the Wigner functions show negativity depth (see text). Insets show the multiphonon contributions charts for different states. Gray horizontal lines indicate thresholds of corresponding multiphonon non-Gaussianity. Black numbers show the multiphonon non-Gaussianity depth of the conditional states (the number of quanta of thermal noise needed to be added for the corresponding probability to be reduced below the non-Gaussianity threshold).

quantum state of the pulse of light of duration τ at the detector. In the Heisenberg picture, it reads (see SM for derivation)

$$\mathcal{A}_{\text{det}}(\tau) = \sqrt{1-\zeta} \left[\sqrt{T} a_m(0) + \sqrt{1-T} a_N \right] + \sqrt{\zeta} a_{\text{vac}}, \quad (5)$$

where \mathcal{A}_{det} is the annihilation operator of the temporally filtered mode of light (instantaneous field operator $a_{\text{det}}(t)$) with filtering function $f^{\text{out}}(t)$:

$$\mathcal{A}_{\text{det}}(\tau) = \int_0^\tau a_{\text{det}}(t) f^{\text{out}}(t) dt. \quad (6)$$

Hereinafter we address this mode as the *detector mode*.

In Eq. (5), T is the effective readout transmittance (readout efficiency). This transmittance depends on the parameters of the optomechanical interaction (coupling rate, linewidths of cavity and the mechanics)

Figure 3: Comparison of the cuts through Wigner functions of the bunched states at the output that approximate the Fock state $|10\rangle$. (a) Bunching of $N = 10$ copies of single-phonon-added thermal state via HBT. (b) $N = 5$ copies of two-photons-added thermal state with additional delay nearly sufficient to lose 10-photon non-Gaussianity. Without the additional delay, the two panels would be identical. The gray dashed line is the theoretical Wigner function of the Fock state $|10\rangle$. Insets show multiphoton contributions $[\langle k | \rho | k \rangle]$ of the mechanical states, gray line shows the absolute threshold of 10-photon non-Gaussianity $p_{10}^G = 0.654$, the number near the bar shows the corresponding non-Gaussianity depth (in units of the added noise phonons required to break the quantum non-Gaussianity). For blue lines, the initial thermal state is the ground state, for the yellow lines, it is $\rho_{\text{th}}(0.2)$.

and the choice of the temporal filtering function $f^{\text{out}}(t)$. In the derivation of T it is assumed that the optomechanical cavity has only one output channel (no internal losses). Moreover, in our simulations, we assumed the optimal filtering function f^{out} that maximizes T . The problem of finding the optimal temporal modes of flying degrees of freedom has been studied in e.g. [64, 65]. The internal cavity losses, loss in propagation towards the detector, and the detector inefficiency are accounted for in Eq. (5) by the effective transmittance ζ , and the corresponding vacuum noise a_{vac} .

Figure 4: Quantum non-Gaussianity of the states of light at the detector. (a) Wigner function cuts of the single-phonon-added (blue lines) and two-phonon-added (yellow lines) thermal states, assuming perfect readout $\zeta = 0$ (full lines) and the value of ζ at which multiphoton QNG vanishes. The corresponding value of ζ (in units $-10 \log_{10} \zeta$ dB) is written above the bars in (b,c). Initial occupation of the mechanical oscillator $n_0 = 0.05$. Gray dashed lines show Wigner functions of ideal Fock states $|1\rangle$ and $|2\rangle$. Numbers near the dips of the Wigner functions show the loss ζ (in dB) required to lose the negativity. (b,c) multiphoton probabilities of the state of light at the detector corresponding to lines in (a). Dashed horizontal lines show thresholds of multiphoton QNG.

The quantum state of the optimal detector mode is studied at Fig. 4. First, the estimations show that with the optimal set of parameters, the optimal detector mode is, in principle, capable of almost a perfect state swap from the mechanics ($T \approx 1$). Consequently, the limiting factor for the verification is the nonzero loss ζ . In Fig. 4, we visualize the detector mode states showing their Wigner functions and multiphoton probabilities. We can see that the determinative factor of the possibility of verifying the QNG character of the mechanical state is the efficiency of the detection scheme $1 - \zeta$. Curiously, due to the presence of higher Fock states contributions in the conditional states, slightly more than 50 % of loss is required to rid

Figure 5: Estimation error of phase-randomized displacement evaluated according to the quantum Cramér-Rao bound (Eq. (9)). We assume $M = 500$ copies of the probe state. Color lines correspond to phonon-added thermal states, solid lines: to the initial ground state, and dashed lines: to the initial thermal state with mean occupation $n_0 = 0.05$ phonons. Yellow lines: single phonon added, blue lines: two phonons added. Gray lines of various dashing correspond to the example probe states, as indicated by the labels: Fock states and thermal state $\hat{\rho}_* = \rho_{\text{th}}(0.05)$ with mean occupation 0.05. The table below indicates the coefficient of linear fit of the estimation error for different states as a function of N_c in the region $N_c \leq 0.3$ where the dependencies are approximately linear. Different columns correspond to Fock states $|0\rangle$ and $|m\rangle$ and to the addition of different numbers of phonons to different initial states: \mathbb{A} – single-phonon addition, \mathbb{A}^2 – two-phonon addition.

the conditional Wigner functions of negativity (an attenuated single-photon state $\zeta|0\rangle\langle 0| + (1 - \zeta)|1\rangle\langle 1|$ loses its negativity exactly at $\zeta = 1/2 \approx 3.01$ dB).

2.4 Estimation of phase-randomized displacement

In this section, we consider theoretically sensing a phase-randomized displacement [50] using the phonon-engineered states as an example of their practical applicability. We show that adding one or two phonons to a thermal state significantly increases its sensing capabilities. For full derivations, see Section 6.

A phase-randomized displacement of magnitude $\sqrt{N_c}$ changes the probe state ρ_{in} to ρ_{f} that reads

$$\rho_{\text{f}} = \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{d\phi}{2\pi} \hat{D}(\sqrt{N_c}e^{i\phi})\rho_{\text{in}}\hat{D}^\dagger(\sqrt{N_c}e^{i\phi}) = \sum_n p_{\text{f}}(n|N_c)|n\rangle\langle n|. \quad (7)$$

The last equation represents the output state ρ_{f} is the basis corresponding to the phonon-number resolved detection characterized by the POVM $|k\rangle\langle k|$, $k \in \mathbb{N}_0$. Accordingly, the Fisher information of the probe state reads [50]

$$F(N_c) = \sum_n \frac{1}{p_{\text{f}}(n|N_c)} \left(\frac{\partial p_{\text{f}}(n|N_c)}{\partial N_c} \right)^2. \quad (8)$$

The minimal mean-square error $\Delta^2 N_c$ of estimation of N_c attainable by any unbiased estimator is then given by the quantum Cramér-Rao inequality [66, 67]

$$\Delta^2 N_c \geq \frac{1}{MF(N_c)}, \quad (9)$$

where M is the number of copies of the probe state used in the estimation procedure.

Our simulations of the heralded states' capabilities are in Fig. 5. On average, the more phonons are added to the initial thermal state, the lower is the estimation error. The purity of the initial state also increases the sensitivity of the heralded state. Both single- and two-phonon-added thermal states significantly outperform the original thermal state. The error is approximately linear in N_c for small values of N_c (equivalently, the relative error does not depend on N_c). The coefficients of the linear dependence for different probe states are also presented in a table in the caption of Fig. 5. Importantly, perfect phonon-number resolution is not required to achieve this result. The observed levels of errors are reachable already with resolution of up to 2 phonons for single-phonon-added states, and up to 3 phonons for two-phonon-added states. For details, see SM.

3 Discussion and Conclusion

In this manuscript, we propose a scenario for an in-detail study of the QNG nature of multiphonon-added quantum states of mechanical oscillations. Drawing inspiration from the system in [29] that has performed heralding additions and subtractions of phonons to the motion of superfluid Helium, we prove that with feasible parameters, conclusive observation of QNG is possible. Cooling below a feasible mean occupation of $n_0 = 0.2$ allows the generation of mechanical states with one- or two-phonon QNG via the addition of a single or two phonons. Given an available cooling down to a lower mean occupation of approximately $n_0 = 0.05$, it is possible to observe the two-phonon QNG in the leaking light.

The addition of one or two phonons to the thermal state with mean occupation 0.05 significantly enhances its performance for phase-randomized displacement sensing. Further cooling down before the additions, ultimately to the ground state of the mechanical oscillator, brings a larger advantage for such sensing. Importantly, resolution of only a few photons in the detector is needed (up to three for two-phonon-added states, or up to two for single-phonon-added states).

The main limiting factor in the generation and observation of QNG is the thermalization to the mechanical environment. Suppressing the decoherence further would allow continued longer sequences of heralding events reaching higher Fock states, and would improve the purity of conditional mechanical states.

Our analysis is based on several building blocks. First, we assume that by strongly driving the optomechanical cavity we can access the linearized optomechanical interaction. Second, we require operation in the resolved-sideband regime, where the cavity linewidth is much smaller than the frequency of mechanical oscillations. As a result, by detuning the optical drive to the Stokes or anti-Stokes sideband it is possible to address individually one of the two required interactions: beam-splitter-like one on the lower sideband, or the two-mode squeezing one on the upper sideband. The availability of the beam-splitter interaction combined with the low temperature of the mechanical environment (several 20 mK in [29]) grants the possibility of cooling the mechanical oscillations close to the ground state. The addition (or subtraction) of vibrational phonons relies on the possibility of detecting the photons inelastically scattered by the optomechanical interaction. These photons must be detected with as high efficiency as possible, and other photons must be rejected. The high efficiency is guaranteed by using high-quality single-photon detectors [68], and the stray drive photons can be rejected by filtering cavities as in [29].

The analysis presented here stimulates further optomechanical developments in experimental investigations of essential QNG coherence in the superposition of Fock states needed for quantum sensing of phase [38] and binomial error correction codes [39], as already achieved for the trapped ions and superconducting circuits. Moreover, multimode mechanical QNG coherences can be used to advance towards Duan-Lukin-Cirac-Zoller types of communication protocols [24, 69] and mechanical Bell tests [70] in a new regime, and more efficient dual and multi-rail error correction codes [71] developed recently at different platforms. Optical control and efficient readout of such unique mechanical systems in a QNG regime will allow us to overcome the limitations of trapped ions and superconducting experiments in their interconnections.

4 Methods

In this section, we first outline the necessary steps required to describe optomechanical dynamics driven by linearized interaction Hamiltonians, normally occurring in optomechanical experiments in Section 4.1. We then present tools to describe Gaussian states of the optomechanical system and conditional state update by detection in Section 4.2, and to evaluate the multiphonon probabilities and Wigner functions of the conditional states in Section 4.3. A more technical reiteration of these ideas can be found in SM.

4.1 Description of the open optomechanical system dynamics

The standard approach to model weakly coupled optomechanical cavities is by using Heisenberg-Langevin equations of motion [6, 7, 72]. Importantly, pulsed optomechanical dynamics driven by quadratic Hamiltonians can be solved analytically, providing input-output (IO) relations for the operators in the Heisenberg picture. Using these IO relations, it is possible to represent the final quantum state of the system in terms of its initial state and the states of the noise inputs [73]. Such a representation is sufficient to compute the required statistics of the final state. In this section, we derive the optomechanical Hamiltonian and the corresponding Heisenberg-Langevin equations of motion and outline the procedure needed to derive the IO relations. Technical details of the derivations can be found in the SM.

The Hamiltonian of a single-mode optomechanical cavity (with frequency $\omega_c(x_m)$ being a function of the mechanical displacement x_m and decay rate κ) driven at frequency ω_d by a strong coherent light reads ($\hbar = 1$) [54]

$$H = \left[\omega_c + x_m \frac{\partial \omega_c}{\partial x_m} \Big|_{x_m=0} \right] a_c^\dagger a_c + \omega_m a_m^\dagger a_m - i\mathcal{E}(a_c^\dagger e^{-i\omega_d t} - a_c e^{i\omega_d t}). \quad (10)$$

Here $a_{c,m}$ are the annihilation operators of the cavity mode and the mechanical motion. The first term in the Hamiltonian describes the energy of the cavity mode (we expanded the frequency in the Taylor series keeping only the term linear in mechanical displacement x_m). The second term – energy of the mechanical oscillations, and the last term – optical driving with amplitude $\mathcal{E} = \sqrt{2\mathcal{P}\kappa/\omega_d}$ determined by the input laser power \mathcal{P} . The strong coherent drive creates mean classical amplitudes of the optical and mechanical modes given by complex numbers $\alpha_{c,m}$. To continue, we displace the system by these mean amplitudes and shift to the frame rotating with the drive. In this new displaced rotating frame, the Hamiltonian reads

$$H = \Delta a_c^\dagger a_c + \omega_m a_m^\dagger a_m - g(a_c^\dagger + a_c)(a_m^\dagger + a_m) - g_0 a_c^\dagger a_c (a_m^\dagger + a_m), \quad (11)$$

where $\Delta = \omega_c - \omega_d$ is the drive detuning, $g_0 = \omega_c'(x_m = 0)/\sqrt{2m\omega_m}$ is the so-called single-photon optomechanical coupling rate, $g = g_0|\alpha_c|$ is the optomechanical coupling rate enhanced by the mean photon number $\langle n_c \rangle = |\alpha_c|^2$ due to the classical drive. The last term describes a nonlinear coupling that is too weak and is normally omitted which results in the standard linearized optomechanical Hamiltonian [6].

The next logical step is to go to the frame defined by the free oscillations of both modes (first two terms in Eq. (11)). In this frame, the Hamiltonian is further simplified

$$H = \left[g a_c^\dagger a_m e^{-i(\Delta - \omega_m)t} + \text{h.c.} \right] + \left[g a_c a_m e^{i(\Delta - \omega_m)t} + \text{h.c.} \right]. \quad (12)$$

In the case when the strong classical drive is tuned to the (anti-) Stokes sideband, $\Delta = \pm\omega_m$, the Hamiltonian can be further simplified using rotating wave approximation. The necessary conditions of validity of the RWA are high sideband resolution ($\kappa \ll \omega_m$) and weak coupling ($g \ll \kappa, \omega_m$). Determined by the choice of the detuning, the simplified Hamiltonian reads (see Fig. 1):

$$H_{\Delta=\omega_m} = g a_c^\dagger a_m + \text{h.c.}, \quad H_{\Delta=-\omega_m} = g a_c^\dagger a_m^\dagger + \text{h.c.} \quad (13)$$

Using Eq. (13) one can write the equations of motion, e.g. for $a_{c,m}$:

$$\dot{a}_c = i[H, a_c] - \kappa a_c + \sqrt{2\kappa} a_{in}, \quad (14a)$$

$$\dot{a}_m = i[H, a_m] - \frac{\gamma}{2} a_m + \sqrt{\gamma} a_{th}. \quad (14b)$$

Here κ is the cavity linewidth, γ is the mechanical viscous damping rate, and $a_{in,th}$ are the input quantum noises.

Heisenberg-Langevin equations (14) are the first-order ordinary linear differential equations with quantum fluctuating forces. These equations admit an analytical solution that expresses instantaneous values of $a_{c,m}$ in terms of their initial values and the input quantum noises $a_{in,th}$. Using the obtained IO relations, it is possible to fully describe the quantum state of the optomechanical cavity at a given time. The physically motivated case of Gaussian states is described in Section 4.2.

To describe phonon addition and subtraction induced by detecting the leaking photons, one has to also consider the detector mode. To this end, we start with the expression for the field leaking from the cavity towards the detector, which can be written using the optical input-output relations for a high- Q optomechanical cavity [74]

$$a_{out}(t) = -a_{in}(t) + \sqrt{2\kappa} a_c(t). \quad (15)$$

In order to get the expression for the detector mode's ladder operator \mathcal{A}_{det} , we combine its definition (6) with Eq. (15), and substitute the previously obtained solution for $a_c(t)$.

As a result of these manipulations, we obtain the input-output relations that express the operators $a_m(\tau)$, $a_c(\tau)$ and \mathcal{A}_{det} in terms of the operators with known statistics (initial states and the input noises).

4.2 Gaussian statistics and operations

Section 4.1 outlines the procedure to obtain the input-output relations for the operators that describe the system in the Heisenberg picture. Since the input states are all Gaussian and the dynamics are linear, before the detection, the state of the system remains Gaussian and can be described using its first two moments.

In particular, the initial state of the cavity and the state of input optical noise is vacuum, and the initial state of the mechanical oscillator and the input mechanical noise are both in thermal states, with mean occupations, respectively, n_0 and n_{th} .

The output state of the optomechanical interaction prior the detection at time τ is a Gaussian state of the bipartite system, formed by the mechanical oscillator with quadratures and the detector mode. These modes have the quadratures $X_m = (a_m + a_m^\dagger)$ and $P_m = (a_m - a_m^\dagger)/i$ for the mechanics, and $\mathcal{X}_L = \mathcal{A}_{\text{det}} + \mathcal{A}_{\text{det}}^\dagger$ and $\mathcal{P}_L = (\mathcal{A}_{\text{det}} - \mathcal{A}_{\text{det}}^\dagger)/i$ for the optics. In the regime of weak optomechanical coupling ($g \ll \kappa$), which is required for single-phonon operation, it is possible to eliminate the intracavity optical mode (see SM for further elaboration) and consider only the mechanical and the detector mode. The covariance matrix of this system corresponding to the vector of quadratures $(x_m, p_m, \mathcal{X}_L, \mathcal{P}_L)$ can be written in the block form as

$$\mathbb{V} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{C}_{m,m} & \mathbb{C}_{m,L} \\ \mathbb{C}_{m,L}^\top & \mathbb{C}_{L,L} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (16)$$

Here the blocks on the main diagonal describe the covariances of individual modes, mechanics and light, and the off-diagonal blocks describe the correlations. The mean values of the quadratures are all zeroes, thanks to the zero-mean initial quantum states and input noises. Therefore, the covariance matrix contains full information describing the quantum state of the system.

The detector mode is then registered by an on-off detector, which is characterized by a POVM with two elements: $\Pi_0 = |0\rangle\langle 0|$ and $\Pi_1 = \mathbb{1} - \Pi_0$. The operator Π_0 projects the detector mode on vacuum which is a Gaussian operation. The action of the projector Π_1 which corresponds to detecting leaking photons is not Gaussian. However, the state resulting from this detection can be written as a negative combination of two Gaussian operations (see details in SM). Indeed, Π_1 projects the mechanics on a conditional state given by:

$$\rho_{\text{cond}} = \frac{\text{Tr}_L \Pi_1 \rho}{\text{Tr}_{m,L} \Pi_1 \rho} = \frac{\text{Tr}_L \mathbb{1}^m (\mathbb{1}^L - \Pi_0^L) \rho}{\text{Tr}_{m,L} \mathbb{1}^m (\mathbb{1}^L - \Pi_0^L) \rho} = \frac{\text{Tr}_L \mathbb{1}^m \mathbb{1}^L \rho - \text{Tr}_L \mathbb{1}^m \Pi_0^L \rho}{\text{Tr}_{m,L} \mathbb{1}^m \mathbb{1}^L \rho - \text{Tr}_{m,L} \mathbb{1}^m \Pi_0^L \rho} \quad (17)$$

In this expression, $\mathbb{1}^i$ is the identity operator in the space of i -th mode. Furthermore, $\text{Tr}_L \mathbb{1}^m \mathbb{1}^L \rho$ is the partial state of the mechanical mode before the detection, and $\text{Tr}_L \mathbb{1}^m \Pi_0^L \rho$ equals the (unnormalized) conditional mechanical state given no detected photons. The terms in the denominator correspond to the normalization of the states from the numerator. Thanks to the state ρ being Gaussian, there are simple expressions for each of these terms [75]. Therefore, the conditional state of the mechanical oscillator, heralded by a click of the detector, can be written as follows, denoting by $\rho_G(\mathbb{V})$ density matrix of a Gaussian state with covariance matrix \mathbb{V} .

$$\rho_{\text{cond}} = \frac{1}{1 - p_{\text{off}}} [\rho_G(\mathbb{C}_{m,m}) - p_{\text{off}} \rho_G(\mathbb{C}'_{m,m})], \quad (18)$$

where $p_{\text{off}} = 2 [\det(\mathbb{C}_{L,L} + \mathbb{1}_2)]^{-1/2}$ is the probability of the detector not producing a click ("off" result). The conditional covariance matrix \mathbb{C}'_m , corresponding to the detection of vacuum in the leaking light, reads

$$\mathbb{C}'_{m,m} = \mathbb{C}_{m,m} - \mathbb{C}_{m,L} (\mathbb{C}_{L,L} + \mathbb{1}_2)^{-1} \mathbb{C}_{m,L}^\top. \quad (19)$$

For a generalization of this detection scheme to include imperfect detection, a Hanbury-Brown and Twiss measurement, and for the description of multiple subsequent heraldings, see SM.

4.3 Evaluation of non-Gaussianity via multiphonon contributions

The conditional state (18) is a [negative] mixture of two thermal states. Below we extensively use the property that multiple properties of quantum states, such as expectation values of different operators and the Wigner functions are linear in the state.

It is possible to derive effective occupation numbers n_m, n'_m corresponding to these two thermal states:

$$\mathbb{C}_{m,m} = (2n_m + 1)\mathbb{1}_2, \quad \mathbb{C}'_{m,m} = (2n'_m + 1)\mathbb{1}_2. \quad (20)$$

In Fock basis, the diagonal elements of thermal states' density matrices

$$p_k = \langle k | \rho_G((2n + 1)\mathbb{1}_2) | k \rangle = \frac{n^k}{(n + 1)^{k+1}}. \quad (21)$$

Combining Eqs. (18), (20) and (21), we can write

$$\langle k | \rho_{\text{cond}} | k \rangle = \frac{1}{1 - p_{\text{off}}} \left[\frac{n_m^k}{(1 + n_m)^{k+1}} - p_{\text{off}} \frac{(n'_m)^k}{(1 + n'_m)^{k+1}} \right]. \quad (22)$$

And, in general, for a mixture $\rho_{\text{mix}} = \sum_i p_i \rho_G((2n_i + 1)\mathbb{1}_2)$, we can evaluate the diagonal elements using the expression

$$\langle k | \rho_{\text{mix}} | k \rangle = \sum_i p_i \frac{n_i^k}{(1 + n_i)^{k+1}}. \quad (23)$$

This expression can be useful for the evaluation of multiphonon contributions of larger mixtures which we obtain when evaluating multiple phonon additions or subtractions.

Furthermore, the Wigner function corresponding to the conditional state (18) can be written using the fact that the Wigner function is linear in the state. That is, given a mixture of quantum states σ_i with coefficients p_i : $\hat{\sigma} = \sum_i p_i \hat{\sigma}_i$, its Wigner function is a sum of the Wigner functions corresponding to the components of the mixture with the same weights

$$W(x, p; \hat{\sigma}) = \sum_i p_i W(x, p; \hat{\sigma}_i). \quad (24)$$

The last argument of the Wigner function is used to denote the quantum states the functions correspond to. The expression above is valid for arbitrary quantum states $\hat{\sigma}_i$ (not necessarily Gaussian) and arbitrary coefficients p_i .

4.4 Parameters for the simulation

The parameters we use for simulation are extracted from [29, 76] and summarized in Table 1.

Parameter		Value
Mechanical frequency	ω_m	$2\pi \times 315.3$ MHz
Mechanical damping	γ	$2\pi \times 3.12$ kHz
Cavity linewidth	2κ	$2\pi \times 47.2$ MHz
Single-photon coupling	g_0	$2\pi \times 4.6$ kHz
Intracavity power	\mathcal{P}_0	1 μ W
Intracavity photon number	n_{cav}	10^6
Enhanced coupling	g	$\leq 2\pi \times 1$ MHz
Blue-detuned pulse duration	τ_b	2 μ s to 3.5 μ s
Red-detuned pulse duration	τ_r	5.5 μ s to 9.5 μ s
Blue-detuned pulse duration	$\kappa\tau_b$	6×10^2 to 1.1×10^3
Red-detuned pulse duration	$\kappa\tau_r$	1.6×10^3 to 2.8×10^3
Environment temperature	T_{bath}	20 mK
Environment occupation	n_{bath}	1.3

Table 1: Numerical parameters of the superfluid experiment used for the simulations

5 Acknowledgement

The authors thank Jack Harris and Yogesh Patil for helpful discussions. We acknowledge the project 23-06308S of the Czech Science Foundation and project CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004649 of the MEYS Czech Republic supported by the EU funding. R.F. also acknowledges funding from the MEYS of the Czech Republic (Grant Agreement 8C22001), Project SPARQL has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement no. 731473 and 101017733 (QuantERA).

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Supplementary Information for “Quantum Non-Gaussian States of Superfluid Helium Vibrations”

1 Addition and subtraction of single excitations by on-off detectors

The technique to conditionally add or subtract a single excitation by optical heralding is based on the following principles.

Consider a mechanical mode, initially in a state $|\psi_{\text{in}}\rangle$, interacting with an optical mode, initially in a vacuum, via the Hamiltonian of the form (Fig. 1 b)

$$H_{\text{om}} = g(\xi_m a_c^\dagger + \xi_m^\dagger a_c), \quad (\text{S1})$$

where g is the coupling rate, and $\hat{\xi}_m$ is a ladder operator of the mechanical oscillator. In linearized optomechanics, driving on the upper mechanical sideband yields the Hamiltonian Eq. (S1) with $\xi_m = a_m^\dagger$, and driving on the lower sideband, $\xi_m = a_m$ (see Fig. 1 b,c). Interaction for an interval τ under the action of this Hamiltonian will transform the states of the two modes by the action of the unitary operator

$$U_{\text{om}} = e^{-ig\tau(\xi_m a_c^\dagger + \xi_m^\dagger a_c)} \approx \mathbb{1} - ig\tau(\xi_m a_c^\dagger + \xi_m^\dagger a_c) + o(g\tau)^2, \quad (\text{S2})$$

where we assume a weak interaction over a short time. The bipartite state then is transformed as

$$|0_c\rangle \otimes |\psi_{\text{in}}\rangle \mapsto |0_c\rangle \otimes |\psi_{\text{in}}\rangle - ig\tau |1_c\rangle \otimes (\xi_m |\psi_{\text{in}}\rangle). \quad (\text{S3})$$

A consequent detection by the on-off detector (the POVM element $\mathbb{1} - |0\rangle\langle 0|$) removes the vacuum contribution (the first term), and the conditional mechanical state (up to normalization) reads

$$\xi_m |\psi_{\text{in}}\rangle. \quad (\text{S4})$$

The assumptions necessary for this derivation include (i) weak coupling and short interaction time: $g\tau \ll 1$, (ii) unitary optomechanical interaction, which is equivalent to low mechanical noise $\gamma\tau n_{\text{th}} \ll 1$ and $\gamma \ll g$, (iii) good sideband resolution $\omega_m \gg \kappa$ necessary to resolve Stokes and anti-Stokes photons. We also implicitly eliminated the cavity mode, assuming that a_c is the operator that describes the detector mode. This requires pulse durations sufficiently long for the scattered by optomechanical interaction photons to leak from the cavity: $\kappa\tau \gg 1$.

2 Derivation of conditional quantum states of mechanical oscillator

2.1 Equations of motion

Following the standard approach in optomechanics theory [S1], we use the linearized Heisenberg-Langevin equations of motion to study the dynamics of the optomechanical system. In the Heisenberg picture, a quantum state of the system is characterized by a vector of quadratures $\mathbf{r} = (\hat{X}_m, \hat{P}_m, \hat{X}_c, \hat{P}_c)$ with commutation relations $[\hat{X}_i, \hat{P}_i] = 2i$. The equation of motion for this vector reads

$$\frac{d\mathbf{r}}{dt} = \mathbb{A}\mathbf{r} + \mathbf{r}^N, \quad (\text{S5})$$

where \mathbb{A} is the drift matrix, \mathbf{r}^N is the vector of quantum noise inputs, including thermal noise of the mechanical environment and the optical input noise. In the resolved sideband regime ($\omega_m \gg \kappa$), assuming driving on a mechanical sideband ($\Delta = \pm\omega_m$), and a weak coupling ($g \leq \kappa$), the expression for the drift matrix reads

$$\mathbb{A} = \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{\gamma}{2} & 0 & 0 & g_B - g_R \\ 0 & -\frac{\gamma}{2} & g_B + g_R & 0 \\ 0 & g_B - g_R & -\kappa & 0 \\ g_B + g_R & 0 & 0 & -\kappa \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{A}_{m,m} & \mathbb{A}_{m,c} \\ \mathbb{A}_{c,m} & \mathbb{A}_{c,c} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (\text{S6})$$

Each of the matrices $\mathbb{A}_{i,j}$ has dimensions 2×2 . Here γ is the viscous damping rate of the mechanical mode and κ is the optical linewidth. We also formally define the effective linearized coupling rates while driving

on the blue or red sideband $g_{B,R} = g_0 \langle n_{B,R}^{\text{cav}} \rangle^{1/2}$, where $\langle n_{\bullet}^{\text{cav}} \rangle$ is the mean photon number in the cavity due to the drive. Note that these quantities are not simultaneously nonzero: when driving on the lower sideband, $g_B = 0$ and when driving on the upper sideband, $g_R = 0$. The noise vector has elements

$$\mathbf{r}^N = \left(\sqrt{\gamma} x^{\text{th}}, \sqrt{\gamma} p^{\text{th}}, \sqrt{2\kappa} x^{\text{in}}, \sqrt{2\kappa} p^{\text{in}} \right), \quad (\text{S7})$$

with the first two elements being quadratures of the thermal noise and the last two – of the input optical fluctuations. These quadratures satisfy commutation relations

$$[x^i(t), p^i(t')] = 2i\delta(t - t'), \quad i = \text{in, th}. \quad (\text{S8})$$

Eq. (S5) allows a formal solution of the form

$$\mathbf{r}(t) = \mathbb{M}(t)\mathbf{r}(0) + \int_0^t ds \mathbb{M}(t-s)\mathbf{r}^N(s), \quad (\text{S9})$$

where $\mathbb{M}(t) \equiv \exp[\Delta t]$. The solution readily provides an expression for the instantaneous values of the quadratures of the mechanical oscillator as a function of time. Using input-output relations for the light [S2]

$$a^{\text{out}}(t) = -a^{\text{in}}(t) + \sqrt{2\kappa} a^{\text{cav}}(t), \quad \text{where } a^i = \frac{1}{2}(x^i + ip^i), \quad (\text{S10})$$

one can have solutions for the instantaneous amplitude of the leaking light $a^{\text{out}}(t)$. To deal with bosonic statistics of the output light, we have to specify the temporal modes of interest of the output light [S3]. This is done by introducing temporal filtering

$$\mathcal{A}^{\text{det}}(t) = \int_{t-\tau}^t ds a^{\text{out}}(s) f^{\text{out}}(s), \quad (\text{S11})$$

where f^{out} is the *filtering function*. A proper normalization of f^{out} ensures the canonical commutation relations for the filtered temporal mode:

$$\int_{t-\tau}^t ds |f^{\text{out}}(s)|^2 = 1 \Rightarrow [\mathcal{A}^{\text{det}}(t), (\mathcal{A}^{\text{det}}(t))^{\dagger}] = 1. \quad (\text{S12})$$

Correspondingly, the canonical quadratures of this mode, $(\mathcal{X}_L, \mathcal{P}_L) = (\mathcal{A}^{\text{det}} + (\mathcal{A}^{\text{det}})^{\dagger}, i((\mathcal{A}^{\text{det}})^{\dagger} - \mathcal{A}^{\text{det}}))$ satisfy the standard commutation relation $[\mathcal{X}_L, \mathcal{P}_L] = 2i$.

One natural choice of the filtering function is a flat-top pulse: $f^{\text{out}} = \tau^{-1/2}$. The temporal modes corresponding to this filtering function are detected by, e.g., a homodyne detector with a local oscillator with time-independent amplitude. A more optimal choice [S4], from the point of view of reconstruction of the state of the mechanical oscillator, can be done by deriving f^{out} based on the formal solution (S9) of the equations of motion. By substituting Eq. (S9) into Eq. (S10), one gets that the quadratures of the mechanical oscillator enter the expression for the output light as

$$a^{\text{out}}(t) + (a^{\text{out}}(t))^{\dagger} \propto \dots + \mathbb{M}_{3,1}(t) X_m(0). \quad (\text{S13})$$

Accordingly, choosing (up to normalization)

$$f^{\text{out}}(t) = f^{\text{opt}}(t) \propto \mathbb{M}_{3,1}(t), \quad (\text{S14})$$

maximizes the contribution of $X_m(0)$ in $\mathcal{X}_L(t)$. In practice, such filtration can be approximated by postprocessing the results of frequent sampling of the detection with a flat-top filtering function.

$$\mathcal{X}_L = \lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0} \sum_i \frac{C_i}{\sqrt{\Delta t}} \int_{t_i - \Delta t}^{t_i} ds X^{\text{out}}(s), \quad (\text{S15})$$

where C_i are chosen appropriately (e.g. $C_i \approx f^{\text{opt}}(t_i)$).

2.2 Effective Input-Output relations for second moments

The solution of the Heisenberg-Langevin equations allows us to effectively describe the dynamics of the optomechanical system by the relations that map quantum inputs to the outputs following the spirit of [S5]. In practice, the solution for the state of the optomechanical system at the end of a pulse (below for brevity of notation we write it at time $t = \tau$ assuming the pulse begins at $t = 0$) is determined by the initial state of the intracavity field and the mechanical oscillator, and by the quantum state of the input noises. It is convenient to write the input-output relations for the mechanics and the output light separately. We first introduce notation

$$\mathbf{r}^{\text{out}}(\tau) = (X_m(\tau), P_m(\tau), \mathcal{X}_L(\tau), \mathcal{P}_L(\tau)) = \mathbf{r}_m(\tau) \oplus \mathbf{r}_L(\tau), \quad (\text{S16})$$

where \mathbf{r}_k is a vector containing quadratures of the k -th mode, e.g. $\mathbf{r}_m(0) = (X_m(0), P_m(0))$. Then, the solution of the Heisenberg-Langevin equation reads

$$\mathbf{r}_k = \sum_i u_{k,i}(\tau) \mathbb{R}(\theta_{k,i}) \mathbf{r}_i(0) + \sum_j \int_0^\tau ds v_{k,j}(s) \mathbb{R}(\theta_{k,j}) \mathbf{r}_j(s), \quad (\text{S17})$$

where k can take values m, L; i can take values m, c; and j can take values in, th. The scalar functions u_i and v_j are determined by the parameters of the optomechanical interaction, and by the choice of the filtering function. The full form of these functions is too long to present them here, however, they can be straightforwardly derived from Eqs. (S9) to (S11). E.g. $u_{m,c}(\tau) = \mathbb{M}_{1,3}(\tau)$. Finally, rotation matrices $\mathbb{R}(\theta)$ indicate a possible phase rotation introduced by the optomechanical interaction.

The transformations described by Eq. (S17) are linear in quadrature operators which is a consequence of the quadratic Hamiltonian of the system. Given that the initial state of the system is Gaussian, including Gaussian initial states of both intracavity light and mechanical oscillator, as well as Gaussian states of input noises, the output state of the system is also Gaussian. Gaussian states are such states whose Wigner function [S6] is a Gaussian function. These states can be fully described by the first two moments of the quadratures. In our special case, the output state has zero mean values of all the output quadratures, and therefore, can be fully described by its covariance matrix, the matrix with elements

$$\mathbb{V}_{\text{out}} = \text{cov}(\mathbf{r}^{\text{out}}, \mathbf{r}^{\text{out}}) = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{C}_{m,m} & \mathbb{C}_{m,L} \\ \mathbb{C}_{m,L}^\top & \mathbb{C}_{L,L} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (\text{S18})$$

where we define the operation of taking covariance as

$$[\text{cov}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})]_{ij} := \frac{1}{2} \langle \mathbf{x}_i \mathbf{y}_j + \mathbf{y}_j \mathbf{x}_i \rangle - \langle \mathbf{x}_i \rangle \langle \mathbf{y}_j \rangle, \quad (\text{S19})$$

and

$$\mathbb{C}_{A,B} = \text{cov}((X_A, P_A), (X_B, P_B)), \quad A, B = m, L. \quad (\text{S20})$$

In order to compute the covariance matrix from Eqs. (S17) and (S18), one must specify the statistics of all \mathbf{r}_i entering it. In our computations, we assume the intracavity light to be initially in vacuum, the initial mechanical state to be a thermal state with mean occupation n_0 , the input optical and mechanical noise to be Markovian, respectively, in the ground state and in a thermal state with mean occupation n_{th} . There are no cross-correlations between the different modes. This can be summarized as

$$\text{cov}(\mathbf{r}_c(0), \mathbf{r}_c(0)) = \sigma_c \mathbb{1}_2, \quad (\text{S21a})$$

$$\text{cov}(\mathbf{r}_m(0), \mathbf{r}_m(0)) = \sigma_m \mathbb{1}_2, \quad (\text{S21b})$$

$$\text{cov}(\mathbf{r}_{\text{in}}(t), \mathbf{r}_{\text{in}}(t')) = \sigma_{\text{in}} \mathbb{1}_2 \delta(t - t'), \quad (\text{S21c})$$

$$\text{cov}(\mathbf{r}_{\text{th}}(t), \mathbf{r}_{\text{th}}(t')) = \sigma_{\text{th}} \mathbb{1}_2 \delta(t - t'), \quad (\text{S21d})$$

where

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_{\text{in}} = 1, \quad \sigma_m = 2n_0 + 1, \quad \sigma_{\text{th}} = 2n_{\text{th}} + 1, \quad (\text{S22})$$

and the averaging is over the initial state and the state of the environment.

The expressions for $\mathbb{C}_{i,j}$ then read

$$\mathbb{C}_{i,i} = \sum_j T_{i,j} \sigma_j \mathbb{1}_2, \quad \mathbb{C}_{m,L} = \sum_j c_j \sigma_j \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (\text{S23})$$

where i takes values m, L and j takes values c, m, in, th. The coefficients $T_{i,j}$ and c_j indicate the contributions of the quantum inputs of the optomechanical system in its outputs. These coefficients are functions of the pulse duration, the configuration of the optomechanical setup (coupling rate, detuning etc.), and the filtering function that defines the output mode of interest.

2.3 Adiabatic elimination of the cavity mode

In the physically motivated regime of weak optomechanical coupling, the equations of motion for the optomechanical cavity can be significantly simplified by eliminating the intracavity optical mode. Here, we derive the resulting equations of motion and analyze the accuracy of this approximation.

In realistic optomechanical experiments, the cavity decay rate exceeds other rates in the equations of motion (see Eqs. (S5) and (S6)), that is the coupling rate ($g \ll \kappa$) and the inverse pulse duration ($\kappa\tau \gg 1$). In this regime, the intracavity optical mode reacts nearly instantaneously to the changes in the system. Physically, this means that this mode remains almost exactly unpopulated, and its excitations immediately leak from the cavity. Formally, this can be described by equating the derivatives of this mode's quadratures to zero: $\dot{X}_c = \dot{P}_c = 0$. As a result, the equations of motion for this mode get transformed to algebraic equations. We can then rewrite Eq. (S5) in simpler form:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{r}_m}{dt} = \mathbb{A}_{m,m}\mathbf{r}_m + \mathbb{A}_{m,c}\mathbf{r}_c + \mathbf{r}^{\text{th}} \quad (\text{S24})$$

$$\mathbf{0} = \mathbb{A}_{c,c}\mathbf{r}_c + \mathbb{A}_{c,m}\mathbf{r}_m + \mathbf{r}^{\text{in}}. \quad (\text{S25})$$

From these equations, we express the vector of the intracavity quadratures as follows:

$$\mathbf{r}_c = -\mathbb{A}_{c,c}^{-1}\mathbb{A}_{c,m}\mathbf{r}_m - \mathbb{A}_{c,c}^{-1}\mathbf{r}^{\text{in}}. \quad (\text{S26})$$

Substituting this into Eq. (S24) yields

$$\frac{d\mathbf{r}_m}{dt} = [\mathbb{A}_{m,m} - \mathbb{A}_{m,c}\mathbb{A}_{c,c}^{-1}\mathbb{A}_{c,m}] \mathbf{r}_m + [\mathbf{r}^{\text{th}} - \mathbb{A}_{m,c}\mathbb{A}_{c,c}^{-1}\mathbf{r}^{\text{in}}] \equiv \mathbb{A}_{m,m}'\mathbf{r}_m + \mathbf{r}^{\text{th}'}. \quad (\text{S27})$$

The solution for $\mathbf{r}_m(t)$ can be obtained as before, and substituted into Eq. (S26) to obtain the solution for the intracavity quadratures. The latter is required to derive the expression for the leaking light.

Figure S1: Contributions of different inputs in the (a) final state of the mechanics (b,c) quantum state of the leaking pulse as a function of the optomechanical interaction duration. In (a) and (b) the optomechanical coupling rate is $g/\kappa = 4 \times 10^{-3}$, in (c) $g/\kappa = 24 \times 10^{-3}$. Solid lines result from the full solution, thick dashed lines – from the adiabatic elimination of the cavity mode. Different colors correspond to different quantum inputs.

To prove the validity of the adiabatic elimination of the cavity mode, we compare the contributions $T_{i,j}$ defined in Eq. (S23), obtained using the full solution of the Heisenberg-Langevin equations, and the ones resulting from the approximation. The results of the comparison are visualized in Fig. S1, where for sufficiently long interaction $\log_{10}(\kappa\tau) > 30$, the two solutions are virtually indistinguishable.

2.4 Heralding using on-off detectors

Evolution governed by the optomechanical interaction maps initial Gaussian states onto different Gaussian states. The non-Gaussianity in our system emerges from the detection of light using highly nonlinear detectors. Avalanche photodetectors (APDs) perform inherently non-Gaussian measurements and can be characterized by the POVM consisting of two Hermitian operators

$$\hat{\Pi}_0 = |0_L\rangle\langle 0_L|, \quad \hat{\Pi}_1 = \hat{\mathbb{1}}_L - \hat{\Pi}_0, \quad (\text{S28})$$

where $\hat{\mathbb{1}}_L$ is an identity operator in the Hilbert space corresponding to the light mode at the detector. Since $\hat{\Pi}_0$ corresponds to a Gaussian detection (detecting vacuum), the action of this detector can be described using tools of Gaussian quantum information.

Let us apply this knowledge to describe optomechanical heralding. The conditional mechanical state after the detection event reads

$$\rho_m^{\text{cond}} = \frac{\text{Tr}_L[\rho_{mL}\Pi_1]}{\text{Tr}_{m,L}[\rho_{mL}\Pi_1]} = \frac{\text{Tr}_L[\rho_{mL}\mathbb{1}^m(\mathbb{1}^L - \Pi_0)]}{\text{Tr}_{m,L}[\rho_{mL}\mathbb{1}^m(\mathbb{1}^L - \Pi_0)]}. \quad (\text{S29})$$

To further simplify this expression, consider a multimode Gaussian state with a covariance matrix in block form

$$\mathbb{V}_{\text{pre}} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{C}_{A,A} & \mathbb{C}_{A,B} \\ \mathbb{C}_{A,B}^T & \mathbb{C}_{B,B} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (\text{S30})$$

where A and B are collections of modes such that there are N modes in B. A measurement on the modes B that projects these modes on another Gaussian state with CM $\mathbb{R}_{B,B}$, heralds the modes A being in a *conditional state*

$$\rho_{\text{cond}}(\mathbb{V}_{\text{pre}}, \mathbb{R}_{B,B}) = \rho_G(\mathbb{V}_{\text{cond}}(\mathbb{V}_{\text{pre}}, \mathbb{R}_{B,B})). \quad (\text{S31})$$

This is a Gaussian state with CM

$$\mathbb{V}_{\text{cond}}^A(\mathbb{V}_{\text{pre}}, \mathbb{R}_{B,B}) = \mathbb{C}_{A,A} - \mathbb{C}_{A,B}(\mathbb{C}_{B,B} + \mathbb{R}_{B,B})^{-1}\mathbb{C}_{A,B}^T. \quad (\text{S32})$$

The probability of this detection is given by

$$p_{\text{cond}}^B(\mathbb{V}_{\text{pre}}, \mathbb{R}_{B,B}) = \frac{2^N}{\sqrt{\det(\mathbb{C}_{B,B} + \mathbb{R}_{B,B})}}. \quad (\text{S33})$$

From this follows in particular that (skipping $\mathbb{1}^m$ for brevity)

$$\text{Tr}_{m,L} \rho_{mL} \Pi_0 = p_{\text{cond}}^L(\mathbb{V}, \mathbb{1}_2) = p_{\text{off}}, \quad (\text{S34})$$

$$\text{Tr}_L \rho_{mL} \Pi_0 = p_{\text{off}} \rho_G(\mathbb{V}_{\text{cond}}^m(\mathbb{V}, \mathbb{1}_2)) = p_{\text{off}} \rho_G(\mathbb{C}'_{m,m}), \quad (\text{S35})$$

$$\mathbb{C}'_{m,m} = \mathbb{C}_{m,m} - \mathbb{C}_{m,L}(\mathbb{C}_{L,L} + \mathbb{1}_2)^{-1}\mathbb{C}_{m,L}^T, \quad (\text{S36})$$

$$\text{Tr}_L \rho_{mL} \mathbb{1}^L = \rho_G(\mathbb{C}_{m,m}), \quad (\text{S37})$$

$$\text{Tr}_{m,L} \rho_{mL} \mathbb{1}^m \mathbb{1}^L = 1. \quad (\text{S38})$$

Finally, the conditional mechanical state reads

$$\rho_m^{\text{cond}} = \frac{1}{1 - p_{\text{off}}} [\rho_G(\mathbb{C}_{m,m}) - p_{\text{off}} \rho_G(\mathbb{C}'_{m,m})]. \quad (\text{S39})$$

For a generalization to a Hanbury-Brown and Twiss scheme allowing two simultaneous additions/subtractions, see Section 2.6.

2.5 Evolution of heralded non-Gaussian states

The state (S39) is a negative mixture of two Gaussian (thermal) states. Importantly, the result of the action of a quantum map $\Lambda[\bullet]$ on such a sum can be distributed over the individual terms:

$$\Lambda \left[\sum_i p_i \rho_G(\mathbb{V}_i) \right] = \sum_i p_i \Lambda[\rho_G(\mathbb{V}_i)]. \quad (\text{S40})$$

For instance, a single-mode Gaussian map that does not cause phase-space displacement can be written as transforming the covariance matrix as

$$\mathbb{V} \mapsto \mathbb{T}\mathbb{V}\mathbb{T}^T + \mathbb{N}. \quad (\text{S41})$$

The matrices \mathbb{T} (effective transmittance) and \mathbb{N} (added noise) fully describe the map. In particular, for the case of decoherence due to coupling at rate γ over an interval with duration τ_{del} to a thermal bath with mean occupation n_{th} , these matrices read

$$\mathbb{T}_{\text{th}} = e^{-\gamma\tau_{\text{del}}}\mathbb{1}_2, \quad \mathbb{N}_{\text{th}} = (1 - e^{-\gamma\tau_{\text{del}}})(2n_{\text{th}} + 1)\mathbb{1}_2. \quad (\text{S42})$$

Furthermore, the map $\Lambda[\bullet]$ needs not to be Gaussian, it can describe a non-Gaussian operation such as a phonon addition/subtraction. To ensure that there are no ‘‘stray’’ optomechanical correlations with the intracavity field which is implicitly eliminated from the covariance matrix (S18), we assume sufficient delay between subsequent pulses. Indeed, the intracavity field leaks and gets replaced by input vacuum fluctuations at rate κ , which is much faster than the decoherence rate of the mechanical oscillator γ .

2.6 Instantaneous multiple additions/subtractions

To perform an instantaneous two-phonon addition/subtraction, we generalize the scheme with a single APD to an HBT-like scheme with two on-off detectors. The leaking from the optomechanical cavity light (labeled "L") is sent to a balanced beamsplitter with a vacuum ancilla (labeled "A") in the other port. At the two outputs of the beamsplitter, we place on-off detectors. Each of the on-off detectors is characterized by a POVM consisting of two operators:

$$\Pi_0^i = |0_i\rangle\langle 0_i|, \quad \Pi_1^i = \mathbb{1}^i - \Pi_0^i, \quad i = A, L. \quad (\text{S43})$$

Here Π_1^i corresponds to a detection in the arm labeled i , and Π_0^i to no click. Correspondingly, a coincidence count, when both detectors observe a non-zero number of incoming photons, corresponds to the operator $\Pi_1^A \Pi_1^L$. The system comprising mechanics with light and ancilla modes is before the detection in the state ρ_{HBT} . The two clicks, in "L" and "A" modes, project the mechanical mode on the conditional state

$$\rho_m^{\text{HBT}} = \frac{\text{Tr}_{A,L} [\Pi_1^L \Pi_1^A \rho_{\text{HBT}}]}{\text{Tr}_{A,L,M} [\Pi_1^L \Pi_1^A \rho_{\text{HBT}}]}. \quad (\text{S44})$$

We omitted everywhere $\mathbb{1}^M$, and will use shortened notation $\mathbb{1}^M \otimes \mathbb{1}^L \otimes \Pi_0^A \mapsto \Pi_0^A$ in what follows. The state in square brackets can be written as

$$\rho_m^{\text{HBT}} = [(\mathbb{1}^L - \Pi_0^L) \otimes (\mathbb{1}^A - \Pi_0^A) \rho_{\text{HBT}}] = [(\mathbb{1}^{LA} - \Pi_0^L - \Pi_0^A + \Pi_0^L \Pi_0^A) \rho_{\text{HBT}}], \quad (\text{S45})$$

For Gaussian states, this expression can be simplified further.

After the optomechanical interaction, the optomechanical system comprised of the mechanical mode and the leaking light, is in a Gaussian state described by the covariance matrix \mathbb{V}_{ML} . The ancilla is in a vacuum state with covariance matrix $\mathbb{V}_A = \mathbb{1}_2$, so that before the beamsplitter, the three-mode system is also in a Gaussian state with CM $\mathbb{V}_{\text{MLA}} = \mathbb{V}_{\text{ML}} \oplus \mathbb{V}_A$. After the beamsplitter, the state remains Gaussian with the CM that reads

$$\mathbb{V}_{\text{HBT}} = \mathbb{T}_{\text{BS}} \mathbb{V}_{\text{MLA}} \mathbb{T}_{\text{BS}}^T, \quad \mathbb{T}_{\text{BS}} = \mathbb{1}_2 \oplus \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{T} \mathbb{1}_2 & \sqrt{1-T} \mathbb{1}_2 \\ -\sqrt{1-T} \mathbb{1}_2 & \sqrt{T} \mathbb{1}_2 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (\text{S46})$$

For a balanced beamsplitter, $T = 1/\sqrt{2}$. Eventually, the state at the detector has a CM conveniently written in the block form

$$\mathbb{V}_{\text{HBT}} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{C}_{M,M} & \mathbb{C}_{M,L} & \mathbb{C}_{M,A} \\ \mathbb{C}_{M,L}^T & \mathbb{C}_{L,L} & \mathbb{C}_{L,A} \\ \mathbb{C}_{M,A}^T & \mathbb{C}_{L,A}^T & \mathbb{C}_{A,A} \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{S47})$$

Using the notation introduced in Section 2.4, for the numerator of the conditional state

$$\text{Tr}_{\text{AL}}[\rho_{\text{HBT}}] = \rho_G(\mathbb{C}_{M,M}); \quad (\text{S48})$$

$$\text{Tr}_{\text{AL}}[\Pi_0^L \rho_{\text{HBT}}] = p_c(\mathbb{1}^L) \text{Tr}_A \rho_c(\mathbb{1}^L); \quad (\text{S49})$$

$$\text{Tr}_{\text{AL}}[\Pi_0^A \rho_{\text{HBT}}] = p_c(\mathbb{1}^A) \text{Tr}_L \rho_c(\mathbb{1}^A); \quad (\text{S50})$$

$$\text{Tr}_{\text{AL}}[\Pi_0^A \otimes \Pi_0^L \rho_{\text{HBT}}] = p_c(\mathbb{1}^{\text{AL}}) \rho_c(\mathbb{1}^{\text{AL}}), \quad (\text{S51})$$

where all $p_c(\mathbb{O}) = p_c(\mathbb{V}_{\text{HBT}}, \mathbb{O})$, and $\rho_c(\mathbb{O}) = \rho_c(\mathbb{V}_{\text{HBT}}, \mathbb{O})$.

Tracing over certain modes of a Gaussian state simply removes corresponding rows and columns of a covariance matrix. E.g. $\text{Tr}_{\text{AL}} \rho_G(\mathbb{V}_{\text{HBT}}) = \rho_G(\mathbb{C}_{M,M})$. For the probabilities in the denominator

$$\text{Tr}_{\text{ALM}}[\rho_{\text{HBT}}] = 1; \quad (\text{S52})$$

$$\text{Tr}_{\text{ALM}}[\Pi_0^L \rho_{\text{HBT}}] = p_c(\mathbb{1}^L); \quad (\text{S53})$$

$$\text{Tr}_{\text{ALM}}[\Pi_0^A \rho_{\text{HBT}}] = p_c(\mathbb{1}^A); \quad (\text{S54})$$

$$\text{Tr}_{\text{ALM}}[\Pi_0^A \otimes \Pi_0^L \rho_{\text{HBT}}] = p_c(\mathbb{1}^{\text{AL}}). \quad (\text{S55})$$

The conditional state then reads

$$\rho_m^{\text{HBT}} = \frac{\rho_G(\mathbb{C}_{M,M}) - p_c(\mathbb{1}^L) \text{Tr}_A \rho_c(\mathbb{1}^L) - p_c(\mathbb{1}^A) \text{Tr}_L \rho_c(\mathbb{1}^A) + p_c(\mathbb{1}^{\text{AL}}) \rho_c(\mathbb{1}^{\text{AL}})}{1 - p_c(\mathbb{1}^L) - p_c(\mathbb{1}^A) + p_c(\mathbb{1}^{\text{AL}})}. \quad (\text{S56})$$

This is a negative mixture of three Gaussian functions.

3 Criteria of non-Gaussianity

3.1 Photon-number-based criteria

Using non-linear detectors such as on-off ones, and arrays thereof, can drive the initially thermal mechanical oscillations to non-Gaussian states. By definition, these states are the ones whose Wigner functions are non-Gaussian. Given a quantum state ρ of an oscillator, its Wigner function is defined as

$$W_\rho(x, y) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{2ipy} \langle x - y | \rho | x + y \rangle dy. \quad (\text{S57})$$

Non-Gaussianity of this function can be witnessed e.g. by a direct examination, given the full quantum state tomography, or by observing its negative values when the values of the function are known only in certain points of the phase space. The methods relying on the reconstruction of the values of the Wigner function, however, can be demanding in an experiment. Moreover, the negativity of the Wigner function is quickly lost under loss which is a significant obstacle. In practice, more precise methods of non-Gaussianity verification exist, in particular, based on the multiphoton contributions of the quantum states, that is, on the diagonal elements of the density matrix

$$p_k = \langle k | \rho | k \rangle. \quad (\text{S58})$$

In particular, on the plane (p_0, p_1) , only a region of this plane is accessible to Gaussian states [S7, S8]. The region can be parametrized as

$$p_0 = \frac{e^{-d^2[1-\tanh(r)]}}{\cosh(r)}, \quad p_1 = u \frac{d^2 e^{-d^2[1-\tanh(r)]}}{\cosh^3(r)}, \quad (\text{S59})$$

with $d^2 = (e^{4r} - 1)/4$, $0 \leq u \leq 1$, $r \geq 0$. This region is marked by filling in Fig. 1d.

A more fine-grained determination of non-Gaussianity can be performed by having access to photon-number-resolving detection [S9, S10]. In more detail, the n -photon non-Gaussianity is defined as the inability of the state to be represented as a result of an arbitrary Gaussian operation applied to an arbitrary combination of the $n - 1$ lower Fock states. This property is evaluated by finding the upper bounds for the n -photon contributions ($\langle n | \psi \rangle$) of the corresponding states

$$p_n^G = |\langle n | \psi_{n-1} \rangle|^2 = |\langle n | \hat{S}(r) \hat{D}(\alpha) \left[\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} c_i |i\rangle \right]|^2, \quad (\text{S60})$$

where $\hat{D}(\alpha) = \exp[\alpha^* a - \alpha a^\dagger]$ is a displacement operator, and $\hat{S}(r) = \exp[r(a^\dagger)^2 - r^* a^2]$ is a squeezing operator. Observing a matrix element $\langle n | \rho | n \rangle > p_n^G$ thus witnesses a n -photon non-Gaussianity of the state ρ .

4 Quantifiers of non-Gaussian bunching capability

In this section, we derive the normalized Wigner function of the output state of a linear interferometric device with copies of our test state $\hat{\rho}$ entering all n of its inputs. In the extreme case of $n - 1$ outputs being in vacuum, the (unnormalized) quantum state of the remaining output port is denoted $\tilde{W}(x, y)$. Thanks to this state being rotationally symmetric in the phase space, one can write

$$\tilde{W}(x, y) = \tilde{W}(r \cos \phi, r \sin \phi) = w_{\text{out}}(r), \quad (\text{S61})$$

where the expression for w_{out} reads [S11]

$$w_{\text{out}}(r) \propto \sum_{m_1=0}^M \sum_{m_2=0}^M \cdots \sum_{m_n=0}^M \left(\prod_{j=1}^n \frac{p_{m_j}}{m_j!} \right) \frac{(\sum_{i=1}^n m_i)!}{(-n)_{\sum_{i=1}^n m_i}} e^{-\frac{r^2}{2}} L_{\sum_{i=1}^n m_i}(r^2). \quad (\text{S62})$$

Here $r^2 = x^2 + y^2$ is the distance from the phase-space point to the origin, $p_j = \langle j | \hat{\rho} | j \rangle$ are the multiphoton contributions of the state under examination, L_s is the Laguerre polynomial of the order s . To compute the norm, we note

$$\iint_{-\infty}^{\infty} \tilde{W}(x, y) dx dy = w_0 = 2\pi \int_0^{\infty} r w(r) dr. \quad (\text{S63})$$

Computing this last integral yields w_0 which then gives the *normalized* Wigner function

$$W(x, 0) = \frac{2\pi}{w_0} w_{\text{out}}(x). \quad (\text{S64})$$

Moreover, the rotational symmetry of the Fock states and the states that we consider, allows a simplification of computation of the products of the form $\text{Tr}[\rho_1 \rho_2]$. In particular, it is possible to write

$$\begin{aligned} (4\pi)^{-1} \text{Tr}[\rho_1 \rho_2] &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx dy W_1(x, y) W_2(x, y) \\ &= \int_0^{\infty} dr \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi r W_1(r \cos \phi, r \sin \phi) W_2(r \cos \phi, r \sin \phi) \\ &= 2\pi \int_0^{\infty} dr r w_1(r) w_2(r) \quad (\text{S65}) \end{aligned}$$

5 Phonon-subtracted thermal states

Here we briefly elaborate on the process of phonon subtraction. When the effective optomechanical interaction implements excitation hopping, detecting leaking photons heralds the subtraction of a photon from the initial mechanical thermal state. The heralded state approaches an ideal single-phonon-subtracted thermal state (SPSTS, up to normalization $\rho_{\text{SPSTS}} \propto a_m \rho_{\text{th}}(n_0) a_m^\dagger$). In Fig. S2 we compare the optomechanical subtraction with the ideal subtraction to find that the results are barely distinguishable.

Figure S2: Multiphonon contributions of a single-phonon-subtracted thermal state of the mechanical oscillator: $\langle k | \rho | k \rangle$. From left to right, $k = 0, 1, 2$. Blue lines: simulation of the optomechanical subtraction, yellow lines: ideal theoretical SPSTS.

For the ideal SPSTS, multiphonon probabilities equal

$$p_{\text{SPSTS}_n}(n_0) = (n+1) \frac{n_0^n}{(n_0+1)^{n+2}} \leq 4n^n \frac{(n+1)}{(n+2)^{n+2}}. \quad (\text{S66})$$

Unfortunately, despite being quantum non-Gaussian in the sense of criteria Eq. (S59), none of these probabilities exceed the multiphonon QNG thresholds.

6 Detection of phase-randomized displacement

In this section, we consider the effect of a detector capable of resolving only a finite number of phonons. Such a detector is characterized by a POVM comprising operators $\Pi_k = |k\rangle\langle k|$, where k takes integer values between 0 and k_{max} .

Accordingly, Eq. (8) is rewritten as

$$F(N_c) = \sum_{n=0}^{k_{\text{max}}} \frac{1}{p_{\text{f}}(n|N_c)} \left(\frac{\partial p_{\text{f}}(n|N_c)}{\partial N_c} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{p_{k+}} \left(\frac{\partial p_{k+}}{\partial N_c} \right)^2, \quad (\text{S67})$$

Figure S3: Impact of limited photon-number-resolving detectors on the estimation error of phase-randomized displacement. Different panels correspond to different states (notation same as in Fig. 5). Lines with different opacity correspond to different k_{\max} in Eq. (S67), from $k_{\max} = 2$ in the lightest curves, to $k_{\max} = 6$ in the darkest. The graph shows that the lines with $k_{\max} \geq 3$ are indistinguishable.

where

$$p_{k+} = \sum_{n=k_{\max}+1}^{\infty} p_{\mathbb{F}}(n|N_c). \quad (\text{S68})$$

The results of our simulations for the same probe states as in the main text, are in Fig. S3. As is visible from the graph, after increasing $k_{\max} \geq 3$, the estimation error does not reduce further for the two-phonon added states, and $k_{\max} = 2$ is sufficient for single-phonon added states.

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